

The Holistic Process Mining Maturity Model (HP3M)

Dimension	Sub-Dimension	PM Initiated	Diagnostic and Descriptive (2)	Predictive	Prescriptive
Technology	Information Capability	Get process map visualizations, discovery, and conformance checking, deliver simple insights.	Simple analytic with diagnostic and descriptive capability, root cause analysis might be helpful to understand the reason and suggest for some core business process.	Process mining result have predictive capability using AI, using it for alerts and forecasting.	The recommendation gives information about what, when, and why an event or trend might happen and tells what actions have the highest potential for the best outcome.
			The analysis result is may linked to value stream Service Level Agreement (SLA's)/ Key Performance Indicator (KPI)'s using dashboard. Sometime AI effort might be detected	The dashboard gives some value with SLA/KPI's that align with business strategy. It also supports daily process management across different department	It allows learning process from historical, prediction and implementation result to triggers situationally aware automations or giving valuable actions needed for the ongoing system

Dimension	Sub-Dimension	Level 1 (Initial)	Level 2 (Managed)	Level 3 (Defined)	Level 4 (Quantitatively Managed)	Level 5 (Optimized)
Data	Data Availability	Recognize relevant data for process mining.	Pay attention to data acquisition standards for process mining.	Propose data acquisition standards for core business units.	Establish data acquisition standards across multiple departments.	Optimize smart data acquisition across all industrial processes within departments.
	Data Security	Have data security plan for IT environment.	Pay general attention to data security management for IT environment.	Make both technical and non-technical plans to deal with data security for core business.	Implement data security management tools and plan across departments.	Optimize data security management and practices across targeted industrial processes.
	Data Quality	Identify the format of input and output for each system.	One-sided and non-historical sample size, difficult to transfer and unstructured data.	Capture essential features but small sample, transferable and semi-structured formats.	Cover relevant features, large sample with equally distributed classes.	Capture all relevant features, large sample, standardized format, structured and metric-scale.
	Data Explainability	Identify the need of data explainability for business process.	Pay attention to dealing with data explainability problems for process mining.	Make plans to deal with data explainability problems for core business process.	Standardize data documentation and consolidation across the organization.	Optimize data explainability across targeted industrial processes within departments.
	Data Privacy	Identify the need of data privacy for business process.	Pay attention to dealing with data privacy problems for process mining.	Make plans to deal with data privacy problems for core business process.	Standardize data privacy and consolidation across the organization.	Optimize data privacy across targeted industrial processes within departments.
Pipeline	Tooling	Use tools with limited capabilities of process mining function.	Use tools for advanced capabilities, define specific business use case.	Use tools connected with ongoing process, generate dashboard for visualization.	Use tools to get data from ongoing system, visualize, and give prediction or alert.	Develop integrated platform with ongoing system, make prediction and prescriptive alerts.
	Integration with Data Source	Data sources need to be downloaded and adjusted to process mining needs.	Data sources standardized to fulfill process mining needs, initial plan for automated integration.	Get integration with data source and create ongoing dashboard.	Ongoing dashboard shows prediction and makes recommendations.	Get most up-to-date data for latest predictive or prescriptive techniques.
	Integration with Operational Application	Independent PM process, not connected with operational application.	Define which operational application can relate to process mining plan.	Use PM experiments to build support for breaking down data silos.	Ongoing dashboards connect with operational application and make suggestions.	PM function connects all needed operational applications throughout the organization.

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Strategic Alignment	Strategy	Align business and technical leaders on the need for Process Mining Awareness.	Use PM Proofs of Concept (POCs) to align leadership on PM investment.	Define PM strategy and communicate to organization, gain budget and sponsorship.	Align PM strategy with organizational roadmaps.	Sustain momentum to keep innovating and transforming.
	Budgeting	No PM Strategy, No PM Budgets.	Short Term Strategy, but no dedicated PM budgets yet.	Short Term Strategy, Dedicated PM Budgets.	Medium Term PM Strategy and Dedicated PM Budgets.	Long Term PM Strategy, Dedicated PM Budgets.
	Business Contribution	No Measure for PM benefit to Business Contribution.	There will be measurement PM benefit in Business Contribution.	Define the number PM benefit for business Contribution.	Give monitoring status for PM benefit for business contribution.	Use business contribution for PM benefit in the Quality Management System as KPI.
Governance	Communication	Understand the consequence and challenge with PM Plan.	Involve different stakeholders to gain complete view of challenges and opportunities.	Synthesize PM Plan to Practice and Guidance.	Build organizational structures to manage the strength and scalability of PM.	Engage with the PM community to compare achievement.
	Quality Metric	Identify PM Implementation in the roadmap.	Translate principles into concrete responsibilities, processes, and metrics.	Standardize governance practices with supporting technology.	Standardize governance practices with Corrective Action.	Standardized governance practice with Preventive Plan.
	Documentation System and Compliance Check	No Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) Established.	SOP Established but Not Fully Implemented.	SOP Implemented and Monitoring Documented.	SOP Implemented, Monitoring Documented and KPI Recorded.	Use feedback from Monitoring and KPI for Continuous Improvement.
	Ownership	Defining process ownership structure, including roles and responsibilities.	Assign process owners to each process based on expertise and knowledge.	Provide process owners with necessary resources and support.	Monitor performance of process owners and provide feedback and support.	Continuously improve the process ownership structure and performance.
Culture	Use Case Availability	See Business Case Urgency but not managed.	See Business Case Urgency, make pilot project use case.	Connect with department to develop solution, use case in specific business case.	Make Standardized Procedure and Integrated in the System.	Create Quality Management Cycle for All Process, Plan-Do-Check-Action (PDCA).
	Management Involvement	Rely on individual for change and problems.	Have initiatives per department but lack of synergy.	Have synergy and communication with another department.	Have business and IT align for integration.	Executive level sponsorship and integration in corporate strategy.
	Adaptability	React on customer problem based on the case.	Start to have customer focus plan, accept customer sound.	Define the standard, procedure based on customer need.	Have measurement for customer need and satisfaction to the business process.	Customer focus strategy, customer insight data as input and optimize it.
	Consistency	No consistency among the process business management.	Recognize the business process and change management.	Define the procedure for change management.	Have mechanism to measure and review the change management.	Optimized step to do continuous improvement in agreement for change management.
People	Skill	Basic understanding of Process Mining workflow, trial on new knowledge.	Ability to perform Process Mining Workflow Available.	Ability to perform data analysis and decision making, understand AI.	Ability to perform complex analysis in Process Mining, may use AI in practice.	Trained in Process Mining integrate with AI and empower other people.
	Responsibility	Define key roles needed to support process mining initiatives.	Define specific responsibilities for each role, form Ad Hoc team.	Create organizational structure that supports process mining initiatives.	Define performance metrics for process mining initiatives.	Evaluate effectiveness of structure, assess roles, and identify improvement opportunities.